

Formation Constants of the Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldoxime with Some Trivalent Metal Ions and UO_2^{2+}

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of UO_2^{2+} , Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Nd^{3+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime. The proton-association constant of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at 25 ± 0.1 . The departure from the electrostatic bond between metal and donor atoms of the reagent has been attributed to the size of the hydrated metal ions of rare earths.

THE oxime of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde has been reported¹ as an excellent reagent for the determination of copper in acidic solutions; a weighable precipitate being formed without the interference from the other metal ions. Endo and Mashima² have used 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime as an analytical reagent for Cu, Zn, Ni and Co in acidic solution. The reagent has also been used as a volumetric reagent for Zn by Mashima³. Some divalent metal complexes of the reagent have been studied by Mayadeo and Kabadi⁴.

In the present communication, the successive formation constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime with some rare earth ions such as Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and divalent UO_2^{2+} have been determined potentiometrically, following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁵.

The Corning model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode in combination with calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale reads 0.005 pH unit.

Experimental

The oxime of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was prepared by dissolving 10 g of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) in about 100 ml of 1N NaOH. To this solution, equimolar quantity of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for about half an hour. On cooling, the solution was filtered and dilute hydrochloric acid was added to the filtrate to get the oxime. It was recrystallised three times using 50 per cent. ethanol to get pure product with m.p. 158° .

The dioxan used for the experimental work was purified⁷. Distilled water was redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate. This distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent. dioxan water (v/v). Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen through the solutions. The free acid, the free acid plus the reagent and the mixture containing metal ion, acid and the reagent were titrated separately against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution. Metal ions other than UO_2^{2+} were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations⁸. UO_2^{2+} was estimated by precipitating with ammonia and weighing it as U_3O_8 after igniting the precipitate in platinum crucible. All measurements were carried out at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard sodium hydroxide (1.04 M).

(i) 5.0 ml HClO_4 (0.16 M) + 5.0 ml NaClO_4 (0.64 M) + 30 ml dioxan.

(ii) 5.0 ml HClO_4 (0.16 M) + 5.0 ml NaClO_4 (0.64 M) + requisite quantity of the reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxan.

(iii) 5.0 ml NaClO_4 (0.64 M) + 5.0 ml metal salt (0.008 M) in 0.16 M HClO_4 + the reagent as in (ii) above + 30 ml dioxan.

The computational method of Irving and Rossotti⁵ was applied to calculate \bar{n} and pL values.

Results and Discussion

In the reagent, it is the phenolic "OH group" which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ion during the formation of metal chelate. Since only one proton per reagent molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves obtained with the solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were evaluated. A curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted from which the value of practical proton association constant $\log {}^pK_{OH}^H$ was calculated by half integral method which corresponds to 'B' value at \bar{n}_A equal to 0.5. $\log {}^pK_{OH}^H$ was also evaluated using the formation function

$\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A} = \log {}^pK_{OH}^H - B$; and selecting the points through $\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$, B plots. The two values agree quite well.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex equilibria. From these formation curves, the values of metal ligand formation (stability) constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\bar{n}=1.5$ respectively.

In the case where formation curves were incomplete, the constants corresponding to 1:1 metal ligand complexes were evaluated by using the formation function

$$\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} = \log K_1 - pL$$

while in the case of 1:2 complexes the formation function used is

$$\log \frac{\bar{n}-1}{2-\bar{n}} = \log K_2 - pL$$

Therefore, selection of points were made through $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}}$, pL plot for evaluation of $\log K_1$ and $\log \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1}$, pL plots for $\log K_2$. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE-1
STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES
 $t=25^\circ$ $\mu=0.1M$

Cations	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	UO ₂ ²⁺
$\log K_1$	11.34	8.24	7.78	8.57	8.89	8.95	11.30
$\log K_2$	-	7.35	-	-	7.56	-	9.61

The values of formation constants reported in Table 1 were determined for the first time in 75:25 dioxan-water (v/v) medium. The order of stability of trivalent metal chelates is found to be

In the case of rare earth complexes, the absence of extensive covalent bonding is indicated by non-availability of 4 f electrons for bond formation due to their shielding by 5 s and 5 p electrons and also their large crystal radii ranging from 0.85 to 1.06 Å. If ionic bonding exists, there shall be increase in stabilities of rare earth complexes with decreasing ionic or crystal radii and according to Born equation, a correlation should exist between metal ligand stability and e^2/r or e/r (where e=charge of gaseous metal ion and r=radius of the ion).

In the present investigation it is seen from the Table 1 that the values of stability constants of rare earth complexes are not as expected from the above consideration, but show marked deviation. Such deviations as suggested by some workers⁹ may be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interaction of 4 f metal orbitals with the ligand field.

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